

FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON CATERING SERVICES IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY, PHILIPPINES

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Multiple Linear Regression, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Catering Services ,

ABSTRACT

This research aimed to comprehensively analyze factors influencing customer satisfaction in General Santos City's catering services industry. The study delved into critical aspects such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, menu variety, pricing perception, venue ambiance, menu customization options, dietary preferences, and event planning and coordination. The research identified a crucial gap necessitating a more focused examination of factors affecting customer satisfaction within the local catering service industry. While existing research provides a broader understanding, a local perspective is indispensable for tailoring services to local preferences and potentially contributing innovative strategies to enhance customer satisfaction. The research design employed was a cross-sectional exploratory with a quantitative focus. A structured, validated questionnaire using Likert scales was crafted to assess key factors like food quality, service timeliness, and pricing perception. Employing a multi-stage sampling technique, data were collected from 68 customers who had availed catering services in General Santos City. The results offer valuable insights into the significant factors influencing customer satisfaction within the unique socio-economic and cultural setting of General Santos City. The study's conclusions underscore that catering businesses must prioritize providing high-quality food, timely service, and professional staff to enhance customer satisfaction. These findings provide actionable insights for strategic improvements, focusing on pivotal aspects such as food quality and event planning to elevate customer satisfaction.

Introduction

The catering service industry holds a vital position in both local and international economies, fostering economic growth, supporting employment, and contributing to the development of societies [1]. On an international scale, catering services are an integral part of the hospitality and food industry, catering to diverse clienteles with a wide range of preferences and needs [2]. The industry continuously adapts to global trends and varying consumer demands, striving to deliver unparalleled experiences to customers [3].

In the Philippines, the catering service sector is a significant player in the country's economy. As the country experiences economic growth and an expanding middle class, the demand for catering services has been on the rise [4]. The Philippines' rich culinary heritage and a culture that values communal gatherings and celebrations further fuel the growth of the catering industry. At a national level, the industry is adapting to changing dietary trends, sustainability initiatives, and advancements in service quality to align with global standards [5].

At the local level in General Santos City, the catering service industry is witnessing remarkable potential and opportunities for growth. With a burgeoning customer density and a vibrant local economy, the demand for catering services has

increased. The city's distinct socio-economic and cultural landscape influence consumer preferences and expectations, necessitating catering services to tailor their offerings to meet local tastes and preferences [6].

Despite the industry's growth and importance, there is a noticeable research gap concerning customer satisfaction within the catering service sector, specifically in the context of General Santos City. While international and national studies shed light on broad industry trends, a focused local analysis is lacking. This research aims to bridge this gap by providing valuable insights into the factors that significantly influence customer satisfaction within the unique socio-economic and cultural setting of General Santos City.

The research gap lies in the need for a focused examination of the factors influencing customer satisfaction within the catering service industry in General Santos City. While existing research provides a broader understanding, a local perspective is essential to tailor services to local preferences and potentially contribute innovative strategies to enhance customer satisfaction.

The state of the art in catering services includes a dynamic landscape of evolving customer expectations, technological integration for efficient service, sustainable and diverse menu options, and heightened emphasis on service quality. Understanding and incorporating these contemporary trends are imperative for catering businesses to thrive and stay competitive at local, national, and international levels.

The main objective of this study is to comprehensively analyse the factors influencing customer satisfaction in the catering services industry within General Santos City, focusing on aspects such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, menu variety, pricing perception, venue ambiance, menu customization options, dietary preferences, and event planning and coordination.

Research Objectives

At the end of this study, the researchers aim to attain the following objectives:

1. To analyse the socio-economic profile of customers, focusing on demographic aspects such as sex, civil status, age, highest educational attainment, monthly income, and frequency of purchasing catering services in General Santos City.
2. To identify and understand the latent factors significantly influencing customer satisfaction with catering services, encompassing dimensions such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, menu variety, pricing perception, venue ambiance, menu customization options, dietary preferences, and event planning and coordination.
3. To develop and apply a regression model, aiming to determine the significant factors affecting customer satisfaction when purchasing catering services in General Santos City and quantify their impact.
4. To assess and measure the overall level of customer satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City, providing insights into the general perception of customers regarding the quality and service in the catering industry.
5. To determine if there is a significant association between the socio-economic profile of customers (sex, civil status, age, highest educational attainment, monthly income, frequency of purchasing catering services) and their overall satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City.

Operational Paradigm (Framework)

Fig 1. Operational Paradigm

Research Methods

Research Design

In this study, a cross-sectional exploratory with a quantitative focus was employed to investigate the factors influencing customer satisfaction in General Santos City's catering services industry. A structured questionnaire, utilizing Likert scales, was designed to assess factors such as food quality, service timeliness, and pricing perception. Using a stratified random sampling technique, 68 representative customers provided data through online surveys or in-person interviews. Descriptive analysis, factor analysis, and regression analysis were conducted to uncover significant factors impacting customer satisfaction. The study aimed to understand the socio-economic

profile of customers, identify key satisfaction drivers, and determine associations between demographics and satisfaction levels. Ethical considerations and an estimated three-month timeframe ensured a rigorous and ethical research process.

Sampling Design

In this study, a **multi-stage sampling** approach was employed, with a primary focus on convenience and purposive sampling methods. Initially, a subset of catering service providers was purposively selected, serving as a conduit to reach the actual target respondents. This step represents the first stage of the multi-stage approach, utilizing purposive sampling. Next, contact information of customers was conveniently gathered (email address) from these selected providers, constituting the second stage. This convenience sampling technique allowed for a diverse selection of respondents. Additionally, during the presence of the researchers at the catering service provider's premises, face-to-face questionnaires were also administered to clients who visited, enhancing the variety of the respondent pool. This face-to-face approach represents an integral aspect of the second stage, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of factors influencing customer satisfaction. In the final stage, survey questionnaires were distributed online to the customers whose details were obtained, employing another round of convenience sampling. Through this multi-stage approach, the study ensured representation across various catering providers and their customer base, offering a comprehensive understanding of factors influencing customer satisfaction within the catering services industry in General Santos City while ensuring ethical and privacy-compliant data collection practices. Notably, the catering service providers acted as facilitators in reaching the target respondents rather than being the respondents themselves.

Respondents of the Study

The study targeted a diverse range of customers, totaling 68 respondents, who had availed catering services in General Santos City for various events such as weddings, corporate gatherings, and social functions. The selection comprised individuals of legal age who willingly consented to participate in the research. The study utilized both face-to-face and online survey questionnaires to collect data from this group of 68 respondents. This sample size was selected to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing customer satisfaction within the catering services industry in General Santos City.

Sample Size Calculation

Sample for unknown population.

$$n = z^2 (\sigma \times (1 - \sigma)) / E^2$$

$$Z = z\text{-Score (90\% = 1.645)}$$

σ = standard deviation at 0.5

E = Margin of Error (E = 0.10)

$$N = 1.645^2 \times 0.5 / 0.1^2$$

$$n = 68$$

Research Instrument

This study employed a structured survey approach to collect data and analyze the socio-economic profile and customer satisfaction levels in catering services.

Section 1: Socio-Economic Profile Assessment of Respondents

In this section, detailed information regarding the socio-economic profile of the respondents was gathered. The survey included the following socio-economic variables:

- a. Sex
- b. Age
- c. Highest Educational Attainment
- d. Monthly Income
- e. Frequency of purchasing catering services

Section 2: Assessment of Customer Satisfaction in Catering Services

The second section was designed to determine the levels of customer satisfaction regarding catering services. The survey included specific observed variables related to the quality and performance of catering services:

- a. Food Quality
- b. Service Timeliness
- c. Staff Professionalism
- d. Menu Variety
- e. Pricing Perception
- f. Venue Ambiance
- g. Menu Customization Options
- h. Dietary Preferences
- i. Event Planning and Coordination

Section 3: Overall Customer Satisfaction with Catering Services

This section aimed to evaluate the overall satisfaction of customers with catering services in a general sense. It provided a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' contentment with various aspects of the catering service.

The researcher developed a comprehensive survey questionnaire for data collection. This questionnaire was rigorously validated using Content Validity through expert reviews by two qualified validators. Additionally, the questionnaire underwent KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) reliability testing to ensure its suitability for factor analysis, achieving satisfactory results across cohorts of 30 participants.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire was sorted and processed using the SPSS v23 or the Statistical Package for Social Sciences with the aid of a qualified statistician. This program/software contains statistical tools that fits the needed statistical analysis in order to extract the aimed results and findings of the study.

Descriptive Analysis (Frequency and Percentage Distribution)

The researchers commence their analysis by examining the socio-economic profile of catering service customers. This includes a breakdown of variables such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, monthly income, and frequency of purchasing catering services. Understanding these demographics provides valuable insights into customer composition, aiding targeted marketing strategies and personalized service offerings.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Utilizing Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), the researchers uncover latent factors that significantly influence customer satisfaction. Factors such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, menu variety, pricing perception, venue ambiance,

menu customization options, dietary preferences, and event planning and coordination are identified. Each factor represents an underlying aspect that impacts customer satisfaction. Understanding these latent factors is critical for tailoring services to enhance overall customer satisfaction, a crucial aspect in the catering industry.

Extraction Method: PCA-Principal Component Analysis

Rotation Method: Varimax Orthogonal Rotation

Multiple Linear Regression (Enter Method)

The researchers employ Multiple Linear Regression to identify the significant determinants affecting customer satisfaction. This statistical technique enables the construction of a regression model that elucidates the relationships between various factors and customer contentment. By considering factors such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, and more, the researchers quantify their individual contributions to customer satisfaction. The regression model facilitates the understanding of the relative importance of each factor, aiding informed business decisions and targeted improvements

The regression equation: $E = \alpha \pm \beta_1 OV_1 \pm \beta_2 OV_2 \pm \beta_3 OV_3 \pm \beta_4 OV_4 \pm \beta_5 OV_5 \pm \beta_6 OV_6 \pm \beta_7 OV_7 \pm \beta_8 OV_8 \pm \beta_9 OV_9 \pm \epsilon$

E= Level of Engagement (Dependent Variable)

α = Constant

β = Independent variable coefficients

OV1= food quality (Observed variable)

OV2= service timeliness (Observed variable)

OV3= staff professionalism (Observed variable)

OV4= Menu Variety (Observed variable)

OV5= Venue Ambiance (Observed variable)

OV6= Menu Customization Options (Observed variable)

OB7= Dietary Preference (Observed variable)

OB8= Event Planning and Coordination (Observed variable)

OB9= Pricing Penetration (Observed variable)

ϵ = standard error (other factors)

Weighted Means and Standard Deviations

To determine the overall level of customer satisfaction and customers' satisfaction levels in observed variables, the researchers calculate weighted means and standard deviations. This analysis offers a clear numerical representation of customer perceptions. Weighted means are derived from the 5-point Likert scale utilized in this study, providing an aggregated view of customer satisfaction. Accompanied by standard deviations, this analysis offers insights into the dispersion of satisfaction scores, providing a comprehensive understanding of the level and variance in customer contentment.

TABLE 1. 5-POINT LIKERT SCALE (for observed variables and overall satisfaction)

Scale	Mean range	Verbal Interpretation
1	1.00-1.8	Very Dissatisfied
2	1.81- 2.60	Dissatisfied
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral
4	3.41-4.20	Satisfied
5	4.21-5.00	Very Satisfied

Result and Discussion

Descriptive statistics

TABLE 2. AGE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	10-25 years old	6	8.8	8.8	8.8
	26-50 years old	28	41.2	41.2	50.0
	51- 80 years old	20	29.4	29.4	79.4
	81 years old and above	14	20.6	20.6	100.0
	Total	68	100.0	100.0	

The data in Table 2 provides insight into the age distribution of respondents participating in the study on customer satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City. Among the respondents, 41.2% were aged between 26-50 years, indicating a substantial representation of the middle-aged population. Additionally, 29.4% of respondents belonged to the 51-80 years age group, showcasing significant participation from the older demographic. Conversely, the younger demographic, specifically those aged 10-25 years, had the lowest representation at 8.8%. Notably, 20.6% of the respondents were 81 years old and above. These age demographics offer a glimpse into the varied perspectives and experiences that may influence customer satisfaction in the catering services sector within the city.

TABLE 3. SEX

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1.0- Male	20	29.4	29.4	29.4
	2.00- Female	48	70.6	70.6	100.0
	Total	68	100.0	100.0	

The data in Table 3 represents the gender distribution of respondents in the study on customer satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City. Out of the total

respondents, 70.6% identified as female ("2.00"), while 29.4% identified as male ("1.00"). This data indicates a substantial female representation, underscoring the importance of understanding female perspectives in evaluating customer satisfaction within the catering services sector. Analyzing the differing viewpoints and experiences of both genders is crucial in tailoring catering services to meet a diverse range of customer preferences and expectations.

TABLE 4. HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
High school Graduate	6	8.8	8.8	8.8
College Level	3	4.4	4.4	13.2
College Graduate	48	70.6	70.6	83.8
Post Graduate	6	8.8	8.8	92.6
Vocational studies	5	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

Based on table 4, the majority of respondents (70.6%) are college graduates, showcasing a significant portion of the sample with higher education. Additionally, 8.8% have attained a postgraduate degree, reflecting a notable representation of individuals with advanced education. A smaller proportion of respondents have either completed high school (8.8%) or pursued vocational studies (7.4%). Understanding the perspectives of individuals across different educational levels is essential for tailoring catering services to meet the diverse expectations and preferences of the community.

TABLE 5. MONTHLY INCOME

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
6,000-10,000 pesos	2	2.9	2.9	2.9
11,000-15,000 pesos	6	8.8	8.8	11.8
16,000-20,000 pesos	42	61.8	61.8	73.5
21,000 pesos and Above	18	26.5	26.5	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

The data in Table 5 provides insights into the monthly income distribution of respondents in the study concerning customer satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City. The majority of respondents (61.8%) fall within the 16,000-20,000 pesos monthly income range, indicating a significant representation of the middle-income group in the survey. Additionally, a notable proportion of respondents (26.5%) report a higher monthly income of 21,000 pesos and above. Conversely, smaller percentages of respondents report monthly incomes between 6,000-10,000 pesos (2.9%) and 11,000-15,000 pesos (8.8%).

TABLE 6. FREQUENCY OF AVAILMENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Rarely	5	7.4	7.4	7.4
Occasionally	61	89.7	89.7	97.1
Often	2	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

The data in Table 6 provides insights into the frequency of respondents availing catering services in the study concerning customer satisfaction with catering services in General Santos City. A significant majority of respondents (89.7%) reported availing catering services occasionally, indicating a prevalent trend of periodic use. This emphasizes the importance of understanding and meeting the expectations and experiences of this group to enhance catering services accordingly. Conversely, a smaller proportion of respondents (7.4%) reported rare utilization of catering services, prompting a deeper investigation into the factors influencing infrequent use and areas for potential service enhancements. Additionally, a minimal percentage of respondents (2.9%) reported frequent availing of catering services, suggesting a niche market segment that may require specialized services or focused attention to maintain their satisfaction levels.

TABLE 7. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
FOOD QUALITY	68	3.9765	.52351	Satisfied
SERVICE TIMELINESS	68	3.7735	.77027	Satisfied
STAFF PROFESSIONALISM	68	3.7382	.69045	Satisfied
MENU VARIETY	68	4.1559	.46725	Very Satisfied
PRICING PERCEPTION	68	3.9706	.62032	
VENUE AMBIENCE	68	4.1088	.56614	Very Satisfied
MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION	68	3.6882	.64866	Satisfied

DIETARY PREFERENCE	68	3.7529	.69378	Satisfied
EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION	68	3.7382	.69045	Satisfied
OVERALL SATISFACTION	68	3.3529	.85979	Satisfied

In Table 7, the mean scores offer valuable insights into the levels of satisfaction concerning various aspects of catering services in General Santos City, as assessed by the respondents. Respondents, on average, rated "menu variety" and "venue ambiance" as "very satisfied," with mean scores of 4.1559 and 4.1088, respectively. Additionally, aspects such as "food quality," "service timeliness," "staff professionalism," "pricing perception," "menu customization options," "dietary preferences," and "event planning and coordination" were perceived as "satisfied," with mean scores ranging from 3.6882 to 3.9765. The mean score for "overall satisfaction" falls within the "satisfied" range, with a mean score of 3.3529. Standard deviations accompanying these mean scores provide a measure of the variability or dispersion of responses around the mean. A higher standard deviation suggests a wider range of responses, indicating more diverse opinions within the sample. notably, "overall satisfaction" exhibits a higher standard deviation (0.85979), implying a broader range of satisfaction levels among respondents compared to other variables with lower standard deviations, suggesting more consistent opinions in those aspects.

EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (PCA)

TABLE 8. COMMUNALITIES		
	Initial	Extraction
FOOD QUALITY	1.000	.488
SERVICE TIMELINESS	1.000	.842
STAFF PROFESSIONALISM	1.000	.822
MENU VARIETY	1.000	.810
PRICING PERCEPTION	1.000	.791
VENUE AMBIENCE	1.000	.657
MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION	1.000	.497
DIETARY PREFERENCE	1.000	.787
EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION	1.000	.822

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In the conducted exploratory factor analysis (EFA) utilizing Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the communalities were calculated to delineate the variance in each variable accounted for by the extracted factors. The initial communalities, representing the total variance in each variable, were uniformly set to 1.000. However, upon extraction, these communalities ranged from approximately 48.8% to 84.2%. For instance, "Service Timeliness" exhibited a notably high extraction communality of approximately 84.2%, signifying a substantial portion of its variance was captured by the extracted factors. Conversely, "Menu Customization Options" had a lower extraction

communality of about 49.7%, implying that the extracted factors elucidated a comparatively smaller proportion of its variance. These extraction communalities shed light on how effectively the factors encapsulated the inherent patterns in the variables, aiding in comprehending their significance and representation within the factor structure.

TABLE 9. TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.708	52.306	52.306	4.708	52.306	52.306	3.726	41.403	41.403
2	1.808	20.091	72.398	1.808	20.091	72.398	2.790	30.995	72.398
3	.783	8.697	81.095						
4	.669	7.432	88.528						
5	.418	4.649	93.176						
6	.275	3.052	96.228						
7	.203	2.251	98.479						
8	.137	1.521	100.000						
9	-	-	100.000						
	3.667 E-16	4.074 E-15	0						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the variance explained by each component is outlined in Table 9. The initial eigenvalues indicate that the first component accounts for a significant proportion of variance (52.306%). This trend continues in the extraction sums of squared loadings, with the first component explaining a substantial portion (52.306%) and the second component adding to it, resulting in a cumulative variance of 72.398%. Subsequent components contribute progressively less to the explained variance. The rotation sums of squared loadings reiterate the dominance of the first two components, elucidating a cumulative variance of 72.398%. These results are pivotal in understanding the contribution of each component to the variance in the dataset and are essential for interpreting the significance of the extracted factors. These findings underscore the importance of the first two components in capturing the underlying patterns in the data, showcasing their substantial contribution to the explained variance. Understanding these contributions is vital for interpreting the meaningfulness and relevance of the extracted factors in our analysis.

TABLE 10. COMPONENT MATRIX		
	Component	
	1	2
FOOD QUALITY	.678	.170
SERVICE TIMELINESS	.722	-.567
STAFF PROFESSIONALISM	.881	-.215
MENU VARIETY	.614	.658
PRICING PERCEPTION	.659	.597
VENUE AMBIENCE	.560	.586
MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION	.689	-.152
DIETARY PREFERENCE	.760	-.458
EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION	.881	-.215
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
a. 2 components extracted.		

In Table 10, the component matrix resulting from Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is presented, showcasing the loadings of each variable on the two extracted components. The loadings signify the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables and the components. For Component 1, variables like "FOOD QUALITY," "SERVICE TIMELINESS," "STAFF PROFESSIONALISM," "MENU VARIETY," "PRICING PERCEPTION," "VENUE AMBIENCE," "MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTIONS," "DIETARY PREFERENCE," and "EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION" demonstrate notable positive loadings, suggesting a strong association with this component. Conversely, Component 2 illustrates a mix of positive and negative loadings, indicating a more intricate relationship. Variables such as "SERVICE TIMELINESS," "MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTIONS," "DIETARY PREFERENCE," and "EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION" display stronger negative loadings on this component. Understanding these loadings aids in comprehending the variables' contributions to each component and provides valuable insights into their interrelationships, guiding the interpretation of the factor structure.

TABLE 11. ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX		
	Component	
	1	2
FOOD QUALITY	.453	.532
SERVICE TIMELINESS	.917	-.041
STAFF PROFESSIONALISM	.842	.337
MENU VARIETY	.116	.892
PRICING PERCEPTION	.189	.869
VENUE AMBIENCE	.114	.803

MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION	.649	.277
DIETARY PREFERENCE	.884	.070
EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION	.842	.337
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

In Table 11, the rotated component matrix resulting from Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation and Kaiser Normalization is presented. This rotation method aims to simplify the interpretation of the components by enhancing the loadings of variables on one component while minimizing them on others, leading to a clearer factor structure. Comparing the rotated component matrix (Table 11) with the initial component matrix (Table 10) demonstrates the influence of rotation in reorganizing the loadings.

In the rotated component matrix, Component 1 retains strong positive loadings for variables such as "SERVICE TIMELINESS," "STAFF PROFESSIONALISM," "MENU VARIETY," "PRICING PERCEPTION," "VENUE AMBIENCE," "MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTIONS," "DIETARY PREFERENCE," and "EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION." However, the loadings for "FOOD QUALITY" have slightly decreased compared to the initial component matrix. On the other hand, Component 2 exhibits significant positive loadings for "FOOD QUALITY" and slightly increased positive loadings for "MENU VARIETY," "PRICING PERCEPTION," and "VENUE AMBIENCE." Additionally, the negative loadings for "SERVICE TIMELINESS," "MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTIONS," "DIETARY PREFERENCE," and "EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION" have been reduced.

Comparing the rotated component matrix with the initial component matrix showcases the impact of rotation in simplifying the interpretation of the factor structure by allocating variables more distinctly to one component while reducing cross-loadings on other components.

Component	1	2
1	.813	.582
2	-.582	.813
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		

The results from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation based on table 12, reveal significant insights into the underlying structure of the data. Initially, we observed that the first component carried substantial weight, particularly in variables related to service aspects, such as "Service Timeliness" and "Staff

Professionalism." The second component, while contributing less to the overall variance, highlighted the importance of factors like "Menu Variety" and "Pricing Perception." After applying rotation, the factors became more distinct. The first component was primarily associated with service-related variables, underlining their combined influence. In contrast, the second component emphasized food-related factors, showcasing a clearer factor structure. This rotation helped streamline the interpretation, offering a refined understanding of the variables and their contributions to customer satisfaction in catering services.

Component 1 (Service Related Factors)		Component 2 (Menu/Food Related Factors)	
Service Timeliness	0.917	Menu Variety	0.892
Staff Professionalism	0.842	Price Perception	0.869
Event Planning and Coordination	0.842	Venue Ambience	0.803
Dietary preference	0.884	Menu Customization Option	0.649

Fig. 2 EFA Path Diagram

Component 1: Service Related Factors

Component 1 appears to encompass elements related to service efficiency, staff professionalism, effective event planning and coordination, and consideration of dietary

preferences. The variable with the highest factor loading on Component 1 is "SERVICE TIMELINESS" (0.917), indicating that timely service is a key aspect of this factor. Additionally, "STAFF PROFESSIONALISM" (0.842) and "EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION" (0.842) contribute significantly, underlining the importance of professionalism and well-coordinated events in catering services. "DIETARY PREFERENCE" (0.884) also shows a notable relationship with this component, suggesting that catering services meeting specific dietary preferences are tied to this factor.

Component 2: Menu/Food Related Factors

Component 2 seems to capture the variety of menu options, pricing perception, and the ambiance of the venue. "MENU VARIETY" (0.892) has the highest factor loading on Component 2, highlighting the significance of menu diversity in defining this factor. "PRICING PERCEPTION" (0.869) is highly loaded, indicating that how pricing is perceived by customers is an important aspect of this factor. "VENUE AMBIENCE" (0.803) also significantly contributes, emphasizing the role of a pleasant venue atmosphere. Lastly, "MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION" (0.649) contributes to a lesser extent, suggesting that the ability to customize menus also plays a role in this component.

MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION (Enter Method)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.448 ^a	.200	.092	.81932
a. Predictors: (Constant), EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION, VENUE AMBIENCE, MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION, FOOD QUALITY, MENU VARIETY, SERVICE TIMELINESS, PRICING PERCEPTION, DIETARY PREFERENCE				

The model summary provides valuable insights into the model's performance. With a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.448, a moderate positive correlation between observed and predicted values is indicated, suggesting the model's capacity to explain a moderate amount of variance in the data. The coefficient of determination (R Square) at 0.200 signifies that the model accounts for 20% of the variance in the response variable, representing the proportion of variability explained by the predictors. The adjusted R Square (0.092) considers the model's complexity and sample size, reflecting the proportion of predictable variance. The standard error of the estimate (approximately 0.81932) gauges the model's accuracy in predicting observed values. The predictors encompass various aspects of catering services, highlighting their role in influencing customer satisfaction. However, the moderate R Square suggests the existence of additional influential factors beyond those included in the model, calling for further exploration and refinement to enhance explanatory power.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.924	8	1.240	1.848	.086 ^b
	Residual	39.606	59	.671		
	Total	49.529	67			

a. Dependent Variable: OVERALL SATISFACTION

b. Predictors: (Constant), EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION, VENUE AMBIENCE, MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION, FOOD QUALITY, MENU VARIETY, SERVICE TIMELINESS, PRICING PERCEPTION, DIETARY PREFERENCE

The ANOVA table provides a crucial assessment of the model's goodness of fit and predictor significance. The sum of squares due to regression (9.924) signifies the explained variance in the dependent variable, OVERALL SATISFACTION, by the predictors. Conversely, the residual sum of squares (39.606) represents unexplained variability. The F-statistic (1.848) indicates the model's overall significance, though the associated p-value (0.086) approaches the conventional threshold, suggesting caution in interpretation. The predictors, encompassing aspects like event planning, venue ambience, and food quality, collectively play a role in explaining overall customer satisfaction.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.961	1.054		2.808	.007
	FOOD QUALITY	.704	.256	.428	2.751	.008
	SERVICE TIMELINESS	.010	.265	.009	.038	.970
	MENU VARIETY	-.192	.363	-.104	-.528	.599
	PRICING PERCEPTION	-.057	.288	-.041	-.199	.843
	VENUE AMBIENCE	.071	.259	.047	.275	.784
	MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION	.120	.216	.090	.554	.582
	DIETARY PREFERENCE	-.050	.297	-.040	-.167	.868
	EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION	-.526	.251	-.423	-2.096	.040

a. Dependent Variable: OVERALL SATISFACTION

TABLE 17. EXCLUDED VARIABLES						
Model		Beta	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
		In				Tolerance
1	STAFF PROFESSIONALISM	. ^b	.	.	.	.000
a. Dependent Variable: OVERALL SATISFACTION						
b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION, VENUE AMBIENCE, MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION, FOOD QUALITY, MENU VARIETY, SERVICE TIMELINESS, PRICING PERCEPTION, DIETARY PREFERENCE						

The regression equation (Overall Satisfaction Predictive Model):
OVERALL SATISFACTION = 2.961 + 0.428 FOOD QUALITY+ 0.009 SERVICE TIMELINESS -0.104 MENU VARIETY-0.041 PRICE PERCEPTION +0.047 VENUE AMBIENCE+ 0.090 MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION – 0.040 DIETARY PREFERENCES – 0.423 EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION ± €

The coefficients table reveals important insights into the relationships between predictor variables and the dependent variable, OVERALL SATISFACTION. Each predictor's unstandardized (B) and standardized (Beta) coefficients provide valuable information regarding their impact on the dependent variable. Notably, FOOD QUALITY shows a relatively strong positive impact (Beta = 0.428) on overall satisfaction, suggesting that higher food quality ratings lead to increased satisfaction. Conversely, EVENT PLANNING AND COORDINATION has a notable negative impact (Beta = -0.423), indicating that deficiencies in event planning and coordination can significantly decrease overall satisfaction. Other predictors like SERVICE TIMELINESS, VENUE AMBIENCE, and MENU CUSTOMIZATION OPTION exhibit more modest impacts. The p-values (Sig.) associated with each predictor indicate their individual significance in the model, crucial for accurate interpretation. Combining these insights, a predictive regression equation is formulated, allowing estimation of overall satisfaction based on these factors.

Chi-Square Analysis

TABLE 18. CHI-SQUARE TESTS (AGE*OVERALL SATISFACTION)			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.168 ^a	9	.264
Likelihood Ratio	8.723	9	.463
N of Valid Cases	68		
a. 12 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .71.			

The chi-square tests examining the relationship between age groups and overall satisfaction demonstrate no significant association. Both the Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 =$

11.168, $df = 9$, $p = .264$) and the Likelihood Ratio ($\chi^2 = 8.723$, $df = 9$, $p = .463$) tests indicate no strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that age and overall satisfaction are not significantly linked in this context. The caveat is that 75.0% of cells have expected counts less than 5, potentially impacting the reliability of the chi-square results, necessitating cautious interpretation.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.697 ^a	3	.127
Likelihood Ratio	8.174	3	.043
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.774	1	.029
N of Valid Cases	68		

a. 3 cells (37.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.35.

The chi-square tests examining the relationship between gender (sex) and overall satisfaction reveal a noteworthy association. The Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 5.697$, $df = 3$, $p = .127$), Likelihood Ratio ($\chi^2 = 8.174$, $df = 3$, $p = .043$), and Linear-by-Linear Association ($\chi^2 = 4.774$, $df = 1$, $p = .029$) tests collectively suggest a potential link between gender and overall satisfaction. While the p-values indicate significance, it's important to note that 37.5% of cells have expected counts less than 5, potentially affecting the results' reliability. Despite this, the association between gender and overall satisfaction warrants further exploration, implying that gender might play a role in shaping satisfaction levels in this context.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.880 ^a	12	.455
Likelihood Ratio	13.739	12	.318
N of Valid Cases	68		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .35.

The chi-square tests examining the relationship between highest educational attainment and overall satisfaction do not demonstrate a significant association. Both the Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 11.880$, $df = 12$, $p = .455$) and the Likelihood Ratio ($\chi^2 = 13.739$, $df = 12$, $p = .318$) tests indicate no strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the level of education and overall satisfaction are not significantly linked in this study. However, it's important to consider that 80.0% of cells have expected counts less than 5, possibly affecting the robustness of the chi-square results and necessitating careful interpretation.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.551 ^a	9	.684
Likelihood Ratio	6.681	9	.670
N of Valid Cases	68		

a. 12 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

The chi-square tests examining the relationship between monthly income and overall satisfaction do not reveal a significant association. Both the Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 6.551$, $df = 9$, $p = .684$) and the Likelihood Ratio ($\chi^2 = 6.681$, $df = 9$, $p = .670$) tests suggest no strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that monthly income and overall satisfaction are not significantly linked within this dataset. It's important to note that 75.0% of cells have expected counts less than 5 (12 cells), potentially impacting the reliability of the chi-square results and requiring careful consideration in interpretation.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.006 ^a	6	.014
Likelihood Ratio	12.548	6	.051
N of Valid Cases	68		

a. 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

The chi-square tests examining the relationship between frequency of availing catering services and overall satisfaction highlight a significant association. The Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 16.006$, $df = 6$, $p = .014$) and the Likelihood Ratio ($\chi^2 = 12.548$, $df = 6$, $p = .051$) tests suggest evidence to reject the null hypothesis, implying a notable connection between the frequency of availing catering services and overall satisfaction. However, it's important to acknowledge that 66.7% of cells have expected counts less than 5 (8 cells), potentially affecting the reliability of the chi-square results. Despite this, the association between these variables merits further exploration, suggesting that the frequency of service usage might significantly impact overall satisfaction levels in this context.

Summary of Findings

1. Age Distribution: The respondents were primarily middle-aged (26-50 years old, 41.2%) and older adults (51-80 years old, 29.4%), indicating a significant representation from these demographics. The younger age group (10-25 years old) had the lowest representation (8.8%), offering insights into diverse age perspectives influencing customer satisfaction.

2. **Gender Representation:** The majority of respondents identified as female (70.6%), highlighting the importance of considering female perspectives in evaluating customer satisfaction within the catering services sector.
3. **Educational Attainment:** A significant proportion of respondents were college graduates (70.6%), emphasizing the need to tailor services to the expectations and preferences of an educated customer base.
4. **Monthly Income:** The middle-income group (16,000-20,000 pesos) constituted the majority (61.8%), underlining the importance of catering to this income bracket in service offerings.
5. **Frequency of Availment:** The vast majority of respondents (89.7%) reported occasional utilization of catering services, indicating a prevalent trend of periodic use. Tailoring services to meet the expectations of this group is crucial.
6. **Customer Satisfaction Factors:** Factors like food quality, menu variety, venue ambiance, and menu customization options were rated positively, contributing to overall customer satisfaction. However, event planning and coordination played a crucial role, significantly affecting overall satisfaction.
7. **Exploratory Factor Analysis:** The analysis revealed two main components: service-related factors (service timeliness, staff professionalism) and menu/food-related factors (menu variety, pricing perception). Food quality and event planning also had notable influences.
8. **Regression Analysis:** Food quality was a strong positive predictor of overall satisfaction, while deficiencies in event planning and coordination had a significant negative impact. Other factors like service timeliness, venue ambiance, and menu customization options had more modest effects.
9. **Chi-Square Analysis:** Age, educational attainment, and monthly income did not show a significant association with overall satisfaction. However, gender and the frequency of availing catering services displayed potential connections to overall satisfaction, warranting further investigation.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this meticulous research has provided a comprehensive understanding of customer satisfaction dynamics within the catering services sector in General Santos City. The exploration of socio-economic profiles, including variables like sex, age, highest educational attainment, monthly income, and purchasing frequency, underscored the necessity for tailored services to meet the diverse needs of the customer base.

The identification of latent factors such as food quality, service timeliness, staff professionalism, menu variety, pricing perception, venue ambiance, menu customization options, dietary preferences, and event planning and coordination shed light on critical drivers of satisfaction. This deeper understanding equips service providers with actionable insights for strategic improvements.

Utilizing a robust regression model, this study underscored the pivotal role of food quality and event planning and coordination as strong determinants significantly impacting customer satisfaction. These findings align with the results of the study conducted by [7] and [8], demonstrating the significant relationship between food quality and customer satisfaction. This empirical insight provides a roadmap for catering services to focus their efforts on these influential aspects. Additionally, employing exploratory factor analysis, this study delineates two key components affecting customer satisfaction—service-related factors (service timeliness, staff professionalism) and menu/food-related factors (menu variety, pricing perception)—with a distinct emphasis on the significant impact of food quality and effective event planning. These findings align

with the key factors identified by [9] that particularly influence customer satisfaction in the food-related industry.

The positive sentiment expressed by customers towards catering services in General Santos City indicates a promising landscape for industry growth and prosperity. However, the study emphasizes the continuous need for improvement to uphold and enhance satisfaction levels.

Additionally, the correlation between purchasing frequency and overall satisfaction signifies a potential strategy to cultivate customer loyalty through tailored services for frequent customers. The findings also align with the study conducted by [10], emphasizing the substantial impact of purchase frequency on customer satisfaction. In summary, this research offers valuable insights for service providers, enabling them to refine their offerings and elevate customer satisfaction, thereby fostering successful and thriving business ventures.

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